

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AND JOB
SATISFACTION, ADJUSTMENT AND ATTITUDE**

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Introduction :-

The Secondary Education Commission (1952-53) said " The most important factor in the contemplated educational reconstruction is the teacher – his personal qualities, his educational qualifications, his professional training and the place that he occupies in school as well as in the community" .Nobody can deny the fact that the role of the teacher is crucial in any teaching learning situation at any level of education. It is the teacher who controls and guides the learning of his students and finally evaluates the outcomes of teaching. He may not decide the goals of education but he is the one who is responsible for the accomplishment of these goals. Attitude of teachers towards teaching play a vital role in their development. Teacher favourable attitude towards teaching are likely to promote creative potentiality of students.

The goal of every teaching is 'effective teaching'. However, only that teaching is successful that brings about effective teaching. How for the teaching is successful can be judged by the results that last and that a learner can does actually use in his life (James, 1958).In spite of universal recognition of the importance of effective teachers, relatively little progress has been made in defining effective teaching or specifying the distinguishing characteristics of effective teachers. What is effectiveness and who is in effective teacher? This is a perplexing question that has eluded an answer even in the countries where educational research has greatly developed. Due to changed political, social and economic conditions in our country, the demands made on teachers are high and varied. Unless there is some clarity about the characteristics of effective teachers, how can the right type of persons be recruited, how can the right type of persons be recruited in this profession of national importance and how can the right type of in-service education be provided to them? It is generally believed that effective teachers are the effective instrument for developing effective human resources in terms of student's growth in desirable direction cartographer

by guardians of the society Various researchers expressed their views about the criterion measure of teaching effectiveness. Most of investigators have given emphasis on personality traits of on effective teacher While some of them have attempted the problem in relation to classroom integration variable ,job motivation, socioeconomic status , job satisfaction and personal growth., Sharma & Ghosh (2006) and Bhandari &patil (2009) studied on job satisfaction. They found that job satisfaction has effects in success in teaching. Some investigators studied Attitude towards Teaching profession. have shown that positive attitude towards teaching profession is related to success in teaching. A few studies have compared effective to success in teachers with ineffective teachers in regard to certain specific variables.

From the above observation it is evident that there is still dearth of research efforts in this vital area.

Objectives

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To compare rural and urban effective teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.
2. To compare rural and urban ineffective teachers relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.
3. To compare effective and ineffective rural teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.
4. To compare effective and ineffective urban teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.

Hypotheses

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. There is no significant difference between rural and urban effective teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.
2. There exist no significant difference between rural and urban ineffective teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.

3. There is no significant difference between effective and ineffective rural teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.
4. There is no significant difference between effective and ineffective urban teachers in relation to their adjustment, job satisfaction and adjustment.

Methodology

Keeping in view the nature of the study, normative survey method was adopted for this study. A sample of 545 secondary teachers was selected from secondary schools. The selected sample of 545 secondary teachers were administered the Teacher's Effectiveness Scale. The score of various teachers on TES were arranged in descending order. The top 27% of the teachers having score 326 and above numbering 149 were classified as effective teachers and bottom 27% of the teachers having score 287% and below numbering 150 were classified as ineffective teachers. Out of 545 secondary school teachers 149 effective and 150 ineffective and 139 rural and 160 urban teachers selected as sample.

Analysis of the Data

The data for the present study was collected with the help of following tools:

- Teacher Effectiveness Scale developed by Kumar & Mutha, 1985.
- Teacher Adjustment Inventory Short Form developed by Managal, 1987.
- Job Satisfaction Questionnaire developed by Kumar & Mutha, 1985.
- Attitude towards Teaching profession Scale developed By Katti & Vannur, 1977.

The results of the study are presented in the following tables:

Table- 1 Comparison between Rural and Urban Effective Teachers on Job Satisfaction Adjustment and Attitude.

S.N	Variable	Effective Urban Teachers (N = 55)		Ineffective Urban Teachers (N = 94)		T value" Df147
		Mean	S D	Mean	S D	
1.	Job satisfaction	21.29	6.15	20.43	6.86	0.77
2.	Adjustment	49.33	7.01	53.02	7.71	2.92**
3.	Attitude	169.24	15.74	168.50	15.49	0.28**

An examination of table-1, reveals that 't' values of job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude are 0.77, 2.92 and 0.28 respectively. 't' value is insignificant in respect of job satisfaction and attitude whereas it is significant at 0.01 level in respect of adjustment. This shows that there is no significant difference between rural and urban school effective teachers as far as job satisfaction and teaching attitude are concerned whereas there exists high significant difference between rural and urban school effective teachers in the field of professional adjustment.

Table-1, also reveals that mean score of effective teachers on job satisfaction and attitude are 21.29 and 169.24 respectively which are higher than those of urban effective teachers. It is therefore concluded that rural effective teachers are more satisfied with respect to their job and have better teaching attitude. However, mean score on adjustment shows that urban school effective teachers have relatively better professional adjustment than their rural counterparts.

Table-2 Comparison between Rural and Urban School Ineffective Teachers on Job Satisfaction, Adjustment and Attitude

s. n	Variable	Effective Urban Teachers (N = 84)		Ineffective Urban Teachers (N = 66)		T value" Df 148
		Mean	S D	Mean	S D	
1.	Job satisfaction	17.24	4.95	18.77	5.98	1.72
2.	Adjustment	48.35	8.16	46.56	9.30	1.25
3.	Attitude	145.90	14.72	148.92	15.63	1.24

Table-2, concluded that 't' values of job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude are 1.72 and 1.24 respectively. The 't' value is not significant with respect to job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude. This indicates that there is no significant difference between rural and urban school ineffective teachers as far as job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude are concerned. Table-2, also depicts that mean scores of job satisfaction and attitude of urban ineffective teachers are 18.77 and 148.92 respectively which are higher than those of rural ineffective teachers. It is therefore concluded that urban ineffective teachers are more satisfied with respect to their job and have better teaching attitude. However, the mean scores

of rural ineffective teachers on adjustment is relatively better professional adjustment than their urban counterparts.

Table-3 Comparison between Effective and Ineffective Rural Teachers on Job Satisfaction, Adjustment and Attitude

S.N.	Variable	Effective Urban Teachers (N = 55)		Ineffective Urban Teachers (N = 55)		T value" (df 137
		Mean	S D	Mean	S D	
1.	Job satisfaction	21.29	6.15	17.24	4.95	4.28*
2.	Adjustment	149.33	7.01	48.35	8.16	0.73
3.	Attitude	169.24	15.74	145.89	14.72	8.89**

Table-3 shows that 't' value of job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude for effective and ineffective rural teachers are 4.28, 0.73 and 8.89 respectively. 't' value significant at 0.01 level in case of job satisfaction and attitude and insignificant in case of adjustment. This reflects that there is significant difference between effective and ineffective rural teachers as for as job satisfaction significant difference between effective and ineffective rural teachers. The mean scores of effective rural teachers on job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude are 21.29, 149.33 and 169.24 respectively which are higher than the corresponding scores of ineffective rural teachers. Thus it can be concluded that effective rural teachers have better adjustment and attitude and are more satisfied in respect to their job compared to ineffective counterparts.

Table-4 Comparison between Effective and Ineffective Urban Teachers on Job Satisfaction, Adjustment and Attitude

S.N.	Variable	Effective Urban Teachers (N = 55)		Ineffective Urban Teachers (N = 84)		t value" Df 137
		Mean	S D	Mean	S D	
1.	Job satisfaction	20.43	6.86	18.98	5.98	1.58
2.	Adjustment	53.02	7.71	46.56	9.30	4.79**
3.	Attitude	168.54	15.49	148.97	15.63	7.82**

* Significant at .01 level of significance

Table-4, indicates that the 't' value of job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude for ineffective and effective urban teachers as 1.58, 4.79 and 7.82 respectively. The 't' value is significant at 0.01 level in case of adjustment and attitude and is not significant in case of job satisfaction. This implies that there is significant difference between effective and ineffective urban teachers as far as adjustment and attitude are concerned. However there is no significant difference between effective and ineffective urban teachers on job satisfaction. The mean scores of effective urban teachers on job satisfaction, adjustment and attitude are 20.43, 53.02 and 168.50 respectively which are higher than corresponding scores of ineffective urban teachers. Therefore, it is concluded that effective urban teachers have better professional adjustment and attitude and are more satisfied in respect of their jobs as compared to ineffective urban teachers.

Major Findings

- On the basis of analysis and interpretation of data, major conclusions have been drawn regarding effectiveness in relation to adjustment, job satisfaction and attitude towards teaching profession.
- Effective rural school teachers are found to be more satisfied with their jobs and have better teaching attitude. However, effective urban school teachers have relatively better adjustment.
- Ineffective rural school teachers have relatively better adjustment but lesser teaching attitude and job satisfaction compared to their urban counterparts.
- Significant difference is inferred between effective and ineffective rural school teachers as far as job satisfaction and attitude are concerned while adjustment does not make significant difference.
- There is significant difference between effective and ineffective urban school teachers in the field of adjustment and attitude whereas no significant difference exists on job satisfaction.

Conclusion

On the basis of above findings it can be said that rural teachers are more job satisfied. Whereas effective rural and urban teachers are job satisfied, adjusted and having positive attitude. Effectiveness of teaching contributes a pivotal role in these dimensions. Effective teacher can adjusted easily in any type of environment. For gaining these types of characteristics in teachers the environment of teacher education should be improved. If the teacher education institutions produce effective teachers, it is obvious that our students, rather our future fruit bearing citizen will also be good quality.

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